

Social Media – the Art Nouveau of Communicating Research Projects to Citizens?

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1. Introduction

Beneficiaries of public research funding, such as the European Horizon programme¹, have a responsibility to ensure a wide dissemination of project results and in particular to engage in communicating outcome to the wider public. We, the authors of this article, are a group of consultants and practitioners in materials modelling, as well as educators and experts versed in communicating and disseminating project results. We contribute to writing scientific papers to engage with the expert community, attend and present at conferences, and collaborate widely with the help of online meeting platforms. In similar ways, we engage with industry and, additionally, enrol them to work with us, to do case studies and invite their contributions to expert meetings in order to experience the outcome of our research first hand. With policy makers we engage via personal contacts and roadmaps where we lay out what should happen in the next 20 years or so. However, the question is how best to engage with members of the civil society and make our research and development more accessible to them. We would like to demonstrate to them what our research can do to be meaningful to everyone and we are very keen to engage with younger persons who have not yet made ultimate career decisions.

We took a few steps back in history and researched if civil society ever was at the receiving end of scientific findings. Indeed, it was – via the niche demographics of wealthy men and a few female exceptions. The knowledge transfer happened in school-like settings and required some literacy by eligible members of civil society. The advent of compulsory schooling helped civil society to gain the necessary literacy to self-educate more and scientists turned to languages other than Latin to distribute their findings.

During the centuries, other media of knowledge transfer appeared. Civil society in general is very inquisitive and visual and likes the odd sanguinary detail; hence, public dissections were of great interest for some time. Also, museums appeared, where collectors showed off their souvenirs from afar and besides impressing society may have also taught them a few things about each artefact. Modern museums today have an educational mandate and manage with interactive displays, by employing working scientists, provision of audio guides and didactically well-structured information boards to educate society starting from a young age.

TVs became a standard feature in civil society's dwellings. In 1969, the moon landing was televised (Science+Media Museum, 2019), and an estimated 650 million viewers watched Armstrong's first steps on the Moon's surface. This was indeed one of the most iconic NASA project outcomes to be shown to civil society.

Visual media remain a valuable channel to educate the wider population, but the receiving screen has moved on to computers and handheld devices. With the emergence of social media platforms, we can now engage with global civil society more directly. With these platforms, there is a renewed importance and opportunity to use illustrations to convey content or accompany the written word. The last section of this paper is dedicated to YouTube, LinkedIn, X and Instagram and we will share how we use them to reach #civilsociety and how well we manage the Art Nouveau of becoming content creators and disseminating to the wider world.

¹ https://rea.ec.europa.eu/horizon-europe-dissemination-and-exploitation_en

2. Science Communication to the Citizens of the World – A Retrospective

Our main research and development we perform in EU projects falls under Natural Sciences, Engineering and/or Computer Sciences which may not feature in day-to-day conversations people have in social settings. Hence, we wanted to shed light on how and if scientific content was provided to the general public in the past, and if they found it palatable. As often, one starts a retrospective in Ancient Greece, as Aristotle is referred to as the first scientist (Lo Presti, 2014). However, science or, better, knowledge communication should be merited to Plato, who in the early decades of the 4th century BC founded the Academy (Trelawny-Cassity, 2022) in Athens, where Aristotle studied. The academy was open to the public, and the main participants were upper-class men²; hence it was not limited to scholars only but certainly to the wealthy and literate. Scholasticism (New World Encyclopedia contributors, 2019), best described as a method of learning taught by the academics of medieval universities around 1100 – 1500, "rediscovered" the collected works of Aristotle. Monastic schools formed and became the basis of the earliest European medieval universities, and Scholasticism dominated education in Europe to around 1700. Again, education was limited to either clerics or wealthy men. Moreover, the tomes were written in Latin, Ancient Greek and Arabic which excluded the general public to enjoy the scientific findings of the time.

In 1632, Galileo Galilei challenged the traditional Ptolemaic system and also the de facto standard of learned communication by writing a book in support of the Copernican world view in the Italian language (*Dialogo sopra i due massimi sistemi del mondo*)³. While it took the Holy See until 1992 (Montalbano, 1992) to accept that the earth orbits the sun, writing in Italian immediately enabled many more people to read the book and, thus, made it accessible to a wider audience. Still, it required people to be literate to be able to read Galilei's *dialogo*, but compulsory schooling and affordable books did conquer Europe. In the German state of Gotha, first modern public schools were opened in 1524, influenced by Martin Luther (McKinney, 2017). The idea was to make education as compulsory as military service – for all citizens. Education meant at that time to read and understand the Bible in German; but nevertheless, wider parts of the German population became literate and this idea fortunately spread to other parts of Europe and beyond. What also helped was Gutenberg's invention of a method of printing from movable type (Lehmann-Haupt, 2022) around 1440. Books did not have to be copied by monks by hand anymore and became more available and affordable. The first public library (American Library Association, 2013) funded by a municipality and thus, open for free to all classes of the community, was in Peterborough (New Hampshire, US) in 1833. To these days, the general public gains knowledge from books and other printed media (newspapers, journals) which they may enjoy in a traditional paper format or on electronic devices.

The written word is of course by no means the only way to communicate science; even better is to visualise and demonstrate. In the 16th century, Andreas Vesalius (Cambiaghi, 2017) performed dissections in crowded theatres, and anatomical theatres were built in many cities and the wider public could attend. This stopped in the 19th century as anatomy was practised more seriously and again limited to scholars. In 1991, Gunter von Hagens brought the human body back to the public with his first public BODY WORLDS exhibition, which polarised the audience from its onset. (Burns, 2007) Von Hagens et al. invented Plastination (von Hagens, Tiedemann, & Kriz, 1987), a process designed to preserve the body for educational and instructional purposes. In the public exhibitions, the human

² Two female Philosophers are known, Lasthenia of Mantinea and Axiothea of Phlius (Waithe, 1987)

³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dialogue_Concerning_the_Two_Chief_World_Systems

bodies are presented in ways to permit the audience to see how tissues, organs, muscles, tendons, etc. look like, and also diseased organs and tissues can be studied by the wider public, if they wish to do so.

In London, the Royal Institution (RI) of Great Britain⁴ was founded on 7th March 1799. Its purpose was to introduce new technologies and teach science to the general public through lectures and demonstrations. (James, 2017) (James, 2002) To this day, the RI is famous for its Christmas Lectures which are geared towards a younger audience. They date back to 1825 (Cole, 2012) and have been televised since 1966. Of importance are also the Friday Evening Discourses (James, 2002) which started very informally in 1825 but soon became very popular in Victorian London and are still running. Speakers comprised Dewar, Faraday, and many more personalities of science past and present. The audience are encouraged to wear smart dress and many follow suit, which makes this way of science communication quite a unique experience.

Another way to communicate science to the general public are exhibitions in museums. For example, the Ashmolean Museum (Abt, 2011) in Oxford is the oldest ever, and it opened as Britain's first public museum in 1683. It was a collection of things meaningful to a collector but also of interest to the public as it comprised artifacts from abroad, at a time when travel was only accessible to the very few. Museums still play a huge role in science education of the public and they moved on from mere exhibits to educating, being interactive (Griffin, 1998), involving scientists, dedicated exhibitions and bringing in ideas of modern ways of knowledge transfer. They also will cater for different age groups and aim to engage children from an early age. (Moorhouse, tom Dieck, & Jung, 2019).

In the 20th century, TV sets conquered the living rooms of the general public, and the Coronation⁵ of the late Queen Elizabeth II in 1953, was the moment, when more than 20 million people watched this event and outnumbered the BBC radio audience for the first time. At some point, science discovered this medium as a more entertaining way of communication to the public. In 1969, the moon landing was televised (Science+Media Museum, 2019), and NASA's project outcome was shared with an estimated 650 million members of civil society.

David Attenborough's (Britannica, 2022) television programs date back to the early 1950s on British Television. His most influential work was 1979's *Life on Earth*⁶ which taught the general public about the evolution of life on our planet. Attenborough's work and/or his contributions won 28 awards⁷ and some of them for primetime TV. This is an impressive achievement and gives evidence that the general public do enjoy scientific content if it is presented in an engaging way. Another noticeable television effort was by Jacques Cousteau (Britannica, 2022), who hosted *The Undersea World of Jacques Cousteau*⁸, a documentary television series on American commercial television stations from 1966 to 1976. Another most widely watched series in the history of American public television was *Cosmos: A Personal Voyage*⁹ by Carl Sagan¹⁰, a thirteen-part series on the nature of the universe televised in 1980.

⁴ <https://www.rigb.org/>

⁵ <https://www.bbc.com/historyofthebbc/research/story-of-bbc-television/televisions-crowning-moment/>

⁶ <https://www.imdb.com/title/tt0135095/>

⁷ <https://www.imdb.com/name/nm0041003/awards>

⁸ <https://www.imdb.com/title/tt0192937/>

⁹ <https://www.imdb.com/title/tt0081846/>

¹⁰ <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/people/660/carl-sagan-1934-1996/>

EU projects tend to produce less primetime TV shows but, nevertheless, the H2020 Project OYSTER¹¹ was highlighted during the evening news slot of RAI1 (main TV channel in Italy) and aired on 17th June 2019.¹² The news segment was about “smart surfaces”, and the project coordinator, Prof. Marco Sebastiani from University “Roma Tre” (Italy), was stepping into the lime light.

It is obvious, that new channels of communication are readily adopted by scientists to broadcast their findings to their peers but also to the general public. At the time of writing this paper, social media kept the citizens of the world entertained and Chapter 4 will discuss these new vehicles for communicating science 24/7 to any geographic location with a decent internet connection to any person who is online.

3. Science Communication using Illustrations

This chapter shall be dedicated to illustrating science, since prior to the invention of writing, drawings were the only way of documentation. The cave paintings of Lascaux (France) were created around 15,000 BC, (Tedesco, 2000) and depict wild animals inhabiting the area at that time. Humans were able to interpret their surroundings and record it by using pigments on the walls of a cave. A very first interpretation was, that they may have used these pictures for ceremonial purposes, but today we can use them as a record of what animals have lived there and then. We can also learn what these humans may have hunted and eaten and what predators they may have feared or even venerated. However, other interpretations emerged: In 2018 Sweatman & Coombs (Sweatman & Coombs, 2018) made the case that the purpose of these menageries was to illustrate the star constellations these early humans observed overhead and that these zoophilic representations may have even been the origins of the modern-day zodiac. Very recently Bacon et al. (Bacon, et al., 2023) investigated the sequences of dots, lines and y-shaped markings that appear alongside the depictions of the animals. They worked out that the number of marks were a record, by lunar month, of when the animals were breeding. Notably, Bacon is an independent researcher, and this study is an excellent example of citizen science.

An object found in Germany is more precise about its purpose: The oldest concrete depiction of cosmic phenomena worldwide features on the Nebra Sky Disc. (UNESCO, 2013) (State Museum of Prehistory, 2013) It is about 3,600 years old and was found in Saxony-Anhalt, Germany, and its purpose was to harmonise the solar and lunar calendars. (Deutsche UNESCO-Kommission, 2013). Whilst natural sciences seem to use mundane tools such as pigments and discs to communicate content, our Historian colleagues do have a masterpiece of embroidery stretching seventy metres to tell all about the events surrounding the conquest of England by the Duke of Normandy – the Bayeux Tapestry, 11th Century. It is very rich in detail and provides information about civil and military architecture, armour, and details of everyday life at the time. (The Bayeux Museum, 2021) It also depicts Halley’s Comet (Uri, 2021); certainly, stargazing in stitches.

For a long time, due to the lack of photography, (Meier, 2013) drawings were used to accompany texts and depict what things looked like in real life. For example, Pedanius Dioscorides’ work, *De materia medica*, (Britannica, T. Editors of Encyclopaedia, 2013) was a leading pharmacological text for 16 centuries and some illustrations of plants found their way into later editions. Specifically, with botanical illustrations “*the emphasis is on the scientific record and botanical accuracy to enable identification of a plant*”. (Tyrrell, 2022). This was important to describe plants for medical purposes

¹¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/760827> ; <https://www.oyster-project.eu/>

¹² <https://www.rai.it/dl/RaiTV/programmi/media/ContentItem-d1f3c1ac-2d6b-463e-a31f-134d66929563-tg1.html>

and to avoid poisonous ones. In the Age of Exploration/Age of Discovery (mid-15th – 16th Century) (Mitchell, 2022) geopolitical circumstances demanded Europeans to seek new routes to trade. A side effect was that new countries and ecosystems were discovered, and expeditions were planned specifically to discover these new worlds. Ships often were equipped with artists who documented new fauna and flora by drawing them. An outstanding artist was the Austrian natural history painter Ferdinand Bauer. (Pavid, 2018) He wanted to create the most authentic pictures of the life specimen he saw and developed a four-digit colour referencing scheme for a huge variety of shades and hues. He sketched and marked areas of his artwork with this code and could later colour-in with utmost precision. The power of illustrations to communicate (scientific) content was even used to communicate to potential alien citizens: In 1977, the two space probes Voyager 1 and 2 (Britannica, Voyager, 2022) were sent out to explore and maybe get discovered in space. 115 images¹³ were assembled on the Golden Discs aboard of each vessel and in about 40,000 years may communicate knowledge to some other lifeforms, should there be any.

We also would like to discuss the importance of illustrations (dela Cruz, 2019) in the engineering world: *“drafting, also spelled draughting, also called engineering drawing, graphical representation of structures, machines, and their component parts that communicates the engineering intent of a technical design to the craftsman or worker who makes the product.”* (Kliphardt, 2019) A very famous “draftsman” in history was Leonardo Da Vinci, (Lillis, 2021) who documented in at least 13,000 pages of drawings and notes topics such as anatomy, botany, geology, aerodynamics and hydrodynamics. His approach was very empirical, i.e., based on observation or experience rather than theory or pure logic. For example, Leonardo’s parachute (Britannica, 2010) was built and then tested by British balloonist Adrian Nicholas in 2000, and it did indeed function as anticipated by the Renaissance artist. Draftsmen are still illustrating the engineering world and nowadays often use Computer Aided Design (CAD) software to do so.

From our personal experience as educators and dissemination specialists we can share that illustrations are important to convey knowledge. We need to show to learners how things look like – in the eyes of the educators! We then take our learners on a journey through our minds, describe what we see/infer/deduct and make them experience it with us. For dissemination on social media such as LinkedIn and X we tend to use graphical abstracts where we capture our audience’s attention and convey the most important facts. For Instagram, we developed carousels, i.e., small slide shows comprising illustrations and very few, precise lines of text. In Chapter 4.4, we will describe our work in detail.

4. Social Media and Communicating Science to the Citizens of the World

There are several social media platforms around, but we shall consider a selected few and elucidate how scientists and/or members of EU projects engage with the general public. Even though global social media such as LinkedIn, X and Instagram enable users to find each other wherever they are, there is no global ‘science communication’, as researched by Davies et al. (Davies, et al., 2021). According to their research, science content on social media is delivered differently in European countries, who display a preference for specific platforms. For example, Italy prefers Facebook, the

¹³ <https://voyager.jpl.nasa.gov/galleries/images-on-the-golden-record/>

UK X, and France and Germany YouTube, respectively. Also, there are different communities evolving around single research groups and their Alumni and their respective groups. However, we want to attract everyone to our work, whether they are scientists or not and aim for an approach that goes beyond existing silos.

Cinelli et al (Cinelli, et al., 2022) attempted to answer the questions if social media can become an effective channel to promote engagement in science and if quality content can positively engage users on social media. These authors provided recommendations for trustworthiness and scientific rigour, presentation and style and impact on society - and we tend to agree with them. We find that using links to our project webpage or published peer reviewed papers are helpful in order to appear trustworthy. We developed a particular style on our webpage, i.e., logo, layout, colour scheme, etc. we copy into our social media, so we get an overall identity and become identifiable as a 'brand'. We are also aware of which impact on society we wish to achieve. On YouTube we want to make talks and training accessible and preserve them for the future, on LinkedIn we want to attract professionals to become acquainted with the OntoTrans project, concepts and results. We expect different experts to engage as translators (Klein, et al., 2021) and users. On X we are attempting to provide short information about new developments, and insights to ongoing conferences (ad hoc posts). On Instagram we would like to reach out to young people who have not yet settled on their career path and want to show them in an entertaining way that our project will open new opportunities for them. We also educate on Instagram and explain difficult concepts in a palatable way. We also follow the "the 3Ts' rule" of Cinelli et al. (Cinelli, et al., 2022), i.e., our **type** of a post is always a combination of picture and text as we get most interest when doing so, our **text** includes relevant hashtags and links, and the **time** of posting works for us particularly well on Mondays or Fridays. These findings we extracted from using analysis tools and check what works best to reach a higher number of people.

4.1. YouTube

YouTube¹⁴ is an American online video sharing and social media platform and was launched in 2005, by Steve Chen, Chad Hurley, and Jawed Karim. It was bought by Google (Downey, 2021) in 2006 and is the second most popular social network (Statista, 2024) with 2,5 million users per month. Besides the newest popular music and cat videos, also educational videos on a wide range of topics are uploaded with the intent to inform not only scholars/students but also the public. (Kohler & Dietrich, 2021). YouTube is setup as a platform for leisure and entertainment and one has to envisage how a user may search for content. A user can employ a search bar to look up certain topics and finds a listing of videos ranked by relevance, interaction, and quality – the YouTube search mechanism is confronted with a massive number of videos and does have to "aid" the user in a sensible way. Users interested in particular scientific topics may be prompted about videos depending on their past behaviour. Also, highly rated videos are more likely to be displayed on a user's home page than a video with no "likes" and few views. (Boy, Bucher, & Christ, 2020)

Hence, to engage with the community there we would recommend to generate a so-called channel and get subscribers. Some of the most popular Science Channels (Kharbach, 2022) are, e.g., Crash Course (14,2 million subscribers), SciShow (7,3 million), Periodic Videos (1,57 million), and others.

We applied the search term "H2020 project" to YouTube and did get a list of several project videos, dated three years back that attracted a few 100 to a few 1000 viewers. We also installed a channel for

¹⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/>

EMMC¹⁵, an organisation OntoTrans is related to, and gained experience as “YouTuber” first hand with an OntoTrans channel¹⁶. We could engage some subscribers and posted interviews with industrial project members, recordings of lectures and training our project team gave and the final OntoTrans project video. We reached a few hundred views. The lesson we learned was, one needs to post videos regularly and the effort to do so requires dedicated staff.

4.2. LinkedIn

LinkedIn¹⁷ is an American business and employment-oriented online platform and was launched in 2003. The platform is used for professional networking and career development, and allows job seekers to post their CVs and employers to post jobs. Since December 2016, it has been a wholly owned subsidiary of Microsoft. (Microsoft News Center, 2016) As of August 2024, LinkedIn has over a billion members in more than 200 countries and territories worldwide.¹⁸

LinkedIn Members can put their personal CV online, look for jobs, “link-in” (i.e., connect) with their peers, network and post. Also, companies can have an account and so does OntoTrans.¹⁹ Figure 1 shows a post, seen from a follower’s view. In this instance, the OntoTrans team was inviting persons to fill in a survey about their social media use. A follower can save the post, react to it with a variety of emojis, (Kendall, 2022) share the post, and comment on it.

Figure 1. OntoTrans Post, from a follower’s view

¹⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/c/EuropeanMaterialsModellingCouncil>

¹⁶ https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCYrQJ5ttc_drhtnV3hie73w/

¹⁷ <https://www.linkedin.com/>

¹⁸ <https://about.linkedin.com/>

¹⁹ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/ontotrans-h2020/>

We recommend engaging with others, i.e. not just to share posts, but comment on why a post is meaningful to oneself etc. This not only helps one's followers to understand why and if they may want to investigate further, but also leads to a higher ranking of posts that are displayed to others

A study by Van Norden (Van Noorden, 2014) showed that that scientists mainly tend to use LinkedIn to enable people to contact them, and find contacts, not so much to share research content. We want our H2020 projects to do all of this but also promote our project. We advise our colleagues to keep their CV up to date and continue to connect with professionals as per usual. What we would like them to do as well is to promote themselves via sharing our project OntoTrans' posts and tell their connections what their role/contribution was related to. We in turn link colleagues and projects using "@" in text and use hashtags and aim to follow the suggestions by Cinelli et al. (Cinelli, et al., 2022)

4.3. X

X (former Twitter)²⁰ is a microblogging and social networking service on which users post and interact with messages known as "tweets". Since 2022, X has been owned by Elon Musk who bought it for \$ 44 bn. (Clayton & Hoskins, 2022). As of April 2024, there where over 611 million monthly active users worldwide. (Statista, 2024) A post comprises 280 characters, so one has to type their messages in concise telegram style. This is very good for short and relevant instant messages, for example when attending conference or commenting on real-time happenings. It is also very suitable to share a thought, a picture, a hyperlink to something ones' mind is occupied with and should be shared with likeminded persons all over the globe. Van Norden (Van Noorden, 2014) showed in his study that scientists do use X to follow discussions, research activities of their peers and post work related content. Côté and Darling (Côté & Darling, 2018) ask in their paper whether scientists are engaging broader audiences through social media or not. Scientists starting off with X tend to reach their peers first and stay within the silo of their expertise. The audience heterogeneity rises over time, together with the number of followers increasing. What plays in favour of scientists is that global citizens do increasingly turn to unconventional media sources of information, starting from news up to specific issues they are interested in. Hence, X is a suitable platform to disseminate ones' research/project outcomes, but it requires continuous engagement over a longer time and reaching a certain threshold number of followers, i.e., ideally 1000 upwards. We also recommend using hashtags, as they decide what is trending on X, and people can search by them.

Figure 2 shows the Header of the OntoTrans X account²¹.

²⁰ <https://x.com/>

²¹ <https://x.com/ontotrans>

Figure 2. Header of our OntoTrans X Account

We “mention” our colleagues and related projects using *@user-name* in text – and we gained a followership comprised mostly of our peers. The aim is to work with illustrations and hashtags in text to gain followers beyond our peers and also include hyperlinks. Lundgren et al. (Lundgren, Crippen, & Bex, 2022) discovered that hashtags utilised with the additional elements of hyperlinks and mentions, did lead to higher engagement rates.

A study from Bombaci et al. (Bombaci, et al., 2016) shows that X “... can be used to effectively communicate speakers’ findings to diverse audiences beyond conference walls.” They recommend, amongst other things, to use concise messages to get the speaker’s point across, to widen one’s horizon by following individuals beyond ones’ silo of expertise and use a designated conference hashtag.

Success rates of posts can be investigated via an analytics tool provided by X. One can analyse “impressions”, i.e., times their post was seen on X, and “engagements”, i.e., total number of times a user has clicked on a part of the post, or liked it or re-posted or commented. Hence, it is very straightforward to try new things and see what gains the most “engagements”.

While the landscape has been changing, with some of our peers moving to other platforms such as Mastodon²² most scientists keep both X and Mastodon accounts and do not migrate entirely for the time being. (Irving, 2022)

4.4. Instagram

Instagram²³ is a photo and video sharing app²⁴ developed by Kevin Systrom and Mike Krieger which was launched in 2010. It has around 2 billion monthly active users as of April 2024. (Statista, 2024) We

²² <https://joinmastodon.org/>

²³ <https://www.instagram.com/>

²⁴ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Instagram>

were intrigued by the idea to engage with the younger population as we are very keen to educate the next generation about OntoTrans and related topics. We are aware that it can take five years and more to bring a product on the market during which time a person can do their degrees. Hence, we wanted to let these persons know what is coming their way and what skills they may need for it. This made us create an Instagram account²⁵ for OntoTrans and its header can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Header of the OntoTrans Instagram Account

The next challenge we had was that Instagram requires one picture minimum – thus, we had to become creative. We soon identified our thought processes very much aligned with conceptual art, where “... *the idea or concept is the most important aspect of the work. When an artist uses a conceptual form of art, it means that all of the planning and decisions are made beforehand and the execution is a perfunctory affair.*” (LeWitt, 1967). However, the execution for us was not perfunctory at all but rather of great interest and with enthusiasm we researched tools and existing artworks that could assist us in transforming our ideas and concepts.

Our plan was to create a few slides with as little text as possible and accompany it with graphics. “Slides” on Instagram are of course carousels, which Zote (Zote, 2022) defines as “... *a post containing more than one photo or video, which users can view by swiping left on a post through the phone app. Desktop users can view a carousel post by clicking on the arrow button on the right of a post.*”

We found Canva²⁶ as a suitable design tool to execute our plan and profited from its rich collection of graphics which are free to use.

We colour coded our posts – pink stands for entry-level topics, and turquoise for advanced topics. Both colour schemes are taken from the OntoTrans design portfolio and thus, help us to gain recognisability for the project.

Figure 4 depicts two slides of a pink carousel and the post explains “What are Ontologies?”

²⁵ https://www.instagram.com/ontotrans_h2020/

²⁶ <https://www.canva.com/>

Figure 4. Two slides of a pink Instagram Carousel

The content is not very text heavy and a font that looks like handwriting is used to give the feel these slides were just sketched out for the audience. Graphical elements are used to highlight text and comic-style pictures support the concepts we wish to convey.

The turquoise carousels (Figure 5) convey advanced concepts and relevant fields of application. They show fewer pictures, and offer more text.

Figure 5. Two slides of a turquoise Instagram Carousel "Open Innovation Environments"

The last slides (Figure 6) show a reference to OntoTrans and we invite persons to investigate us further, follow us and find us on other social media.

Figure 6. The last slides of a pink and turquoise carousel, respectively.

We also provide one picture posts (Figure 7) where we share “fast facts”, i.e., we describe an item related to our research, project updates (e.g., newsletters, innovation case videos, etc.) and special days in the calendar, (e.g., European Day of Languages)

Figure 7. Single Slide posts: (a) fast fact (b) project update (c) special day

We also have a special carousel series on persons working on OntoTrans. For that purpose, we interviewed our colleagues and create a persona out of them. That means, we generalise their real self and take away their real identity and gender – hence, our followers can identify with a type of persona they either are or want to be. Figure 8 shows first slides of three of those carousels.

Figure 8. First slides of "Persons working on OntoTrans" Carousels: (a) Polymaths (b) Materials Physicist (c) Materials Modelling Consultants

This series allows us to show to the younger generation how diverse the workforce on our project is and let them recognise certain traits they share with a particular persona. Maybe, they can identify and get an idea to pursue a certain career path. Not all the personas are actual job titles; some reflect a skill set these personas have. OntoTrans promotes an innovative approach, so the actual expert users may not yet exist in companies. However, this is in line with the fact that most jobs that the younger generation will carry out in the future do not yet exist. We also attempt with this series to engage with professionals and whet their appetites to upskill to become one of these expert users in the future.

A collection of our Instagram posts can be found in the accompanying document "OntoTransArt".

5. Conclusions and Outlook

We researched how science was communicated to the general public through the ages and note, that this communication was always happening. Science communicators tended to use the most contemporary vehicles, and as soon as mass media were available, science became accessible to every household. The advent of social media gave science communicators new tools and new ways to reach out to a wider audience. Communicating science to a larger audience is in fact a co-creation process; it requires a lot of skills such as drawing, designing, printing and binding a book, filming, writing software for design platforms, etc. Design software platforms emerged and with the help of graphic designers and artists, who often provide their work for free, scientists can bring their concepts to life and share with a wider audience, now and in the future.

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Disclaimer

All information contained in this study and any opinions expressed in it are intended to share the insights the authors have gained on social media during their work on H2020 Projects. All statements of fact, opinion, or analysis expressed in the report are those of the authors. The information used and statements of fact made are not guarantees, warranties or representations as to their completeness or accuracy. The authors assume no liability for any short term or long-term professional decisions made by any reader based on analysis included in this report.

Acronyms, Abbreviations and Elucidations

BBC - British Broadcasting Corporation; it is the national broadcaster of the United Kingdom and it was founded in 1922.

BC – Before Christ

CAD – Computer Aided Design

EU – European Union; it is a supranational political and economic union of 27 member states that are located primarily in Europe. It was founded in 1993.

H2020 – Horizon 2020 is the financial instrument implementing the Innovation Union, a Europe 2020 flagship initiative aimed at securing Europe's global competitiveness. (2014-2020).

NASA - National Aeronautics and Space Administration; it is an independent agency of the US federal government responsible for the civil space program, aeronautics research, and space research. It was founded 1958.

RAI - Radiotelevisione italiana; it is the national public broadcasting company of Italy and it was founded in 1944.

RI – Royal Institution of Great Britain; it is an organisation for scientific education and research, based in the City of Westminster and it was founded in 1799.

TV - Television

UNESCO - United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization; it is a specialized agency of the United Nations aimed at promoting world peace and security through international cooperation in education, arts, sciences and culture and it was founded in 1945.

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